

First-principles investigation of the thermodynamic stability of MB_2 materials surfaces ($M=\text{Ti}/\text{Zr}/\text{Hf}$)

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Abstract

Some of the renewed interest in transition metal diborides (MB_2 , $M=\text{Ti}/\text{Zr}/\text{Hf}$) arises from their potential use as matrices in ultra-high temperature ceramic matrix composites (UHTCMCs). Crucial to the understanding of such composites is the study of the fibre/matrix interfaces, which in turn requires a deep knowledge of the surface structures and the thermodynamics of the matrix material. Here we investigate the surface stability of MB_2 compounds by first-principles calculations. Five surfaces are stabilised when going from a M -rich to a B-rich environment, respectively $(0001)_M$, $(10\bar{1}0)_M$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$, $(11\bar{2}3)_M$ and $(0001)_B$, with the highly stable $(10\bar{1}0)_M$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and $(11\bar{2}3)_M$ surfaces being discussed here for the first time. The mechanism behind the surface stability is analysed in terms of cleavage energy, surface strain and surface bonding states. Our results provide important information for a better understanding of the most likely surfaces exposed to the fibres in UHTCMCs, thereby for the construction of reliable interfaces and ultimately UHTCMCs models.

Keywords: Surface, Ultra-high temperature ceramics, First principles theory,
Zirconium/zirconium compounds

1. Introduction

Transition metal diborides (MB_2 , $M=\text{Ti}/\text{Zr}/\text{Hf}$) with hexagonal structure (AlB_2 type, space group $P6/mmm$, No. 191) are sound members of the family of ultra high-temperature ceramics (UHTCs). They are extremely heat-tolerant with a melting temperature $T_m > 3000$ °C, elastically

stiff, and in general resistant to chemical attacks and oxidation. At the same time they conduct heat and electricity like metals. These unique and intriguing characteristics have triggered a significant research activity related to aerospace and nuclear applications, as well as in optoelectronic devices. For example, their high tolerance to aggressive environments makes them an ideal matrix for ultra-high temperature ceramic matrix composites (UHTCMCs).¹ In addition, ZrB_2 has been actively studied as buffer layer for the growth of semiconductors due to its good electrical conductivity and excellent lattice match with GaN.²

The surface morphology of MB_2 may largely define the interface adhesion with the fibres in UHTCMCs and with GaN in semiconductor devices, since the most stable surfaces have the highest chance to be exposed to bonding with the other component. It is intuitive to speculate that the B- and M -terminated (0001) surfaces may dominate the surface stability ranking. This is in view of the layered stacking structure along the [0001] direction, suggesting easy delamination. Previous theoretical calculations using first-principles methods suggested the M -terminated (0001) surfaces to be thermodynamically more favourable than the B-terminated counterparts in HfB_2 ,³ ZrB_2 ⁴ and TiB_2 .⁵ However, their relative stabilities with respect to other close packed planes remain unclear.

Of particular interest are the surfaces built along the prismatic $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ planes. They stand out from micro-structure characterisation and mechanical testing. Transmission electron microscopy analysis of ZrB_2 inferred that the prismatic slip was the only identified mechanism responsible for the plastic deformation at room temperature.⁶ The results of nano-indentation and micro-compression tests^{6,7,8} were rationalised by assuming that the interlayer bonding among the $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ prismatic planes was weaker than that between the $\{0001\}$ basal ones. However, a direct comparative investigation of the interlayer bonding along the $\{0001\}$ and $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ directions has not been reported yet. It is then highly desirable to explore the surface stability of the prismatic planes alone, considering their exceptional mechanical properties. In addition to these, it is also interesting to check the surface stability of $\{10\bar{1}1\}$, $\{11\bar{2}0\}$, $\{11\bar{2}2\}$ and $\{11\bar{2}3\}$ as well. A compre-

hensive investigation of the surface structures is essential for a better understanding of the design principles of UHTCMCs.

By using first-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations we have evaluated the cleavage energies and the surface formation energies of MB_2 compounds along the $\{0001\}$, $\{10\bar{1}0\}$, $\{10\bar{1}1\}$, $\{11\bar{2}0\}$, $\{11\bar{2}2\}$ and $\{11\bar{2}3\}$ planes. Here we rank the relative stability of $(0001)_M$, $(10\bar{1}0)_M$, $(11\bar{2}3)_M$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and $(0001)_B$ surfaces, providing a basic model for the construction of the interface structures of UHTCMCs.

2. Calculation methods

First-principles calculations are performed with the VASP code,⁹ which implements DFT within the framework of the plane-wave basis projector augmented wave (PAW) method.¹⁰ The semicore p states of Ti, Zr and Hf are treated as valence electrons in the pseudopotentials. The plane-wave cutoff is set to 500 eV. The exchange-correlation energy is described by the generalised gradient approximation (GGA) with the parametrization of Perdew, Burke and Ernzerhof (PBE).¹¹ Furthermore, the contribution to the bonding due to the van der Waals (vdW) interactions is accounted for by using the semi-empirical Grimme corrections PBE+D2¹² and PBE+D3,¹³ and the Tkatchenko-Scheffler method with iterative Hirshfeld partitioning (PBE+TSH).¹⁴

In addition, the all-electron full-potential electronic structure code FHI-aims¹⁵ is employed to verify our numerical accuracy. All FHI-aims calculations are carried out by using the tier-2 tight basis set and the GGA-PBE functional. For both VASP and FHI-aims calculations, a k -point mesh of $18 \times 18 \times 16$ is used for the unit cell of bulk MB_2 . Those settings converge the total energy within 1 meV/atom. The Brillouin zone of the (0001) , $(10\bar{1}0)$, $(11\bar{2}0)$, $(11\bar{2}3)$, $(11\bar{2}2)$ and $(10\bar{1}1)$ surface supercells (see the structural details in the following section) are sampled with a k -point grids of $16 \times 16 \times 1$, $12 \times 7 \times 1$, $11 \times 14 \times 1$, $18 \times 22 \times 1$, $14 \times 24 \times 1$ and $14 \times 22 \times 1$, respectively.

During the structural optimisation the tolerance over the energy and forces convergence is set to be 10^{-8} eV and 10^{-4} eV/Å⁻¹, respectively. After the full geometry relaxation of the bulk

materials, *ab initio* lattice dynamic calculations are performed to predict the volume expansion in the quasi-harmonic approximation. We use the finite displacement scheme with a $3\times 3\times 3$ supercell (81 atoms) and an atomic displacement of 0.03 Å. Then the force constant matrix is evaluated at various volumes. It is handled by the PHONOPY code^{16,17} to derive the phonon dispersion spectra and the corresponding thermodynamic properties (see the calculation details in the supplementary information - SI).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Bulk and surface structures

The construction of the surface structures is based on bulk MB_2 ($M=\text{Ti}/\text{Zr}/\text{Hf}$), which is investigated first. The lattice constants of bulk MB_2 , a and c , and the c/a ratio, are calculated and summarized in Table 1. We note only very minor differences when comparing the results obtained with the all-electron FHI-aims code and the pseudopotential PAW scheme of VASP. Both display an excellent agreement with experiments^{18,19,20} (a deviation of less than 0.3 % on the lattice parameters). Therefore, the PAW method appears as reliable as an all-electron treatment and will be used in the following.

Table 1: Lattice parameters of bulk MB_2 ($M=\text{Ti}/\text{Zr}/\text{Hf}$) in unit of Å calculated at 0 K with different codes (FHI-aims and VASP) at the GGA-PBE level. In the case of VASP we report additional results obtained with three different treatments of the vdW interaction, all built on GGA-PBE: the Grimme’s PBE+D2 and PBE+D3 corrections, and the Tkatchenko-Scheffler plus Hirshfeld partitioning method (TSH). The experimental values are also reported with their corresponding references.

Structures		Exp.	AIMS: PBE	VASP: PBE (+D2 / +D3 / +TSH)
TiB ₂	a	3.038 ¹⁸	3.032	3.033 (3.018 / 3.004 / 3.007)
	c	3.230 ¹⁸	3.223	3.225 (3.180 / 3.182 / 3.157)
	c/a	1.066	1.063	1.063 (1.054 / 1.059 / 1.050)
ZrB ₂	a	3.170 ¹⁹	3.171	3.172 (3.162 / 3.146 / 3.153)
	c	3.532 ¹⁹	3.541	3.543 (3.493 / 3.510 / 3.475)
	c/a	1.114	1.117	1.117 (1.105 / 1.116 / 1.102)
HfB ₂	a	3.140 ²⁰	3.145	3.144 (3.087 / 3.121 / 3.112)
	c	3.480 ²⁰	3.486	3.488 (3.414 / 3.457 / 3.424)
	c/a	1.108	1.108	1.109 (1.106 / 1.108 / 1.100)

Figure 1: The V - T curve of ZrB_2 calculated by using PBE, PBE+D2 and PBE+D3 methods. The theoretical results are compared with the experimental data of Ref.²¹ Note the excellent agreement provided by the PBE+D2 scheme.

Moreover, the lattice constants calculated at 0 K by using the PBE+D2, PBE+D3 and PBE+TSH methods are also tabulated in Table 1. It is shown that the PBE exchange-correlation functional overestimates the structural parameters by 0.1-0.3 %, and then that the various dispersion corrections contract the lattice constants by an amount varying between 0.3 % and 2.1 %. However, these are results for $T = 0$ K, and a more rigorous comparison with experiments can be obtained only by looking at the volume, V , as a function of temperature. This is done in Fig. 1 for ZrB_2 , where the V - T curve is compared with the experimental results of Ref.²¹ In the temperature range 300-1800 K, the maximum deviations from experiments are 1.7 %, -0.3 % and -1.1 % respectively for PBE, PBE+D2 and PBE+D3. Among them, the PBE+D2 approach performs best. A similar comparison is expected for TiB_2 and HfB_2 , considering their close resemblance²² to ZrB_2 . In the following, we will apply the PBE+D2 functional to the investigation of the MB_2 surfaces.

The atomic structures of the MB_2 surfaces are built up by cleaving the optimized bulk crystal in eight non-equivalent ways, namely $[0001]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}0]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}0]_{B-B}$, $[10\bar{1}1]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}1]_{B-B}$,

$[11\bar{2}0]_{M+B}$, $[11\bar{2}2]_{M+B}$ and $[11\bar{2}3]_{M-B}$. The $[0001]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}0]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}1]_{M-B}$ and $[11\bar{2}3]_{M-B}$ cleaves between the M and the B atomic planes, so to create two different surfaces with either M or B termination. These are respectively denoted as $(0001)_M$, $(0001)_B$, $(10\bar{1}0)_M$, $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$, $(10\bar{1}1)_M$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(B)}$, $(11\bar{2}3)_M$ and $(11\bar{2}3)_B$ according to the surface orientation and the termination species. The $[10\bar{1}0]_{B-B}$ and $[10\bar{1}1]_{B-B}$ cleavage splits the crystal between B only atomic planes, thus making two identical surfaces with B termination, marked as $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(M)}$ and $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$, respectively. They are distinguished with those from M -B cleavage by the species beneath the surfaces (B or M). Lastly, the $[11\bar{2}0]_{M+B}$ and $[11\bar{2}2]_{M+B}$ cleavage creates two identical surfaces with mixed M and B composition, i.e. $(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$ and $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$. For surfaces from the M -B cleavage modes, we adopt the same symmetric termination at both surface ends in order to eliminate dipole effects around the surfaces. A vacuum region of 20 Å is also added beside the cleaved slabs to avoid spurious interaction between adjacent periodic replica of the cell.

In this way twelve types of surface configurations are set up as illustrated in Figs. 2(a) through 2(l). Except for the $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(M)}$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$, $(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$ and $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$ surfaces with stoichiometric composition, all the others from the M -B cleavage modes are non-stoichiometric. For an example, the $(0001)_M$ and the $(0001)_B$ ones, following the $[0001]_{M-B}$ cleavage, have the reciprocal compositions of $(M_3B_6)_n(M_3)$ and $(M_3B_6)_n(B_6)$ (n is the number of B- M bi-layers along the $[0001]$ direction), respectively. The surfaces $(10\bar{1}0)_M$ and $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$, generated from the $[10\bar{1}0]_{M-B}$ cleavage, hold the compositions of $(M_6B_{12})_n(M_6)$ and $(M_6B_{12})_n(B_{12})$, respectively. Similar rules go for the compositions of the $(11\bar{2}3)$ and $(10\bar{1}1)$ surfaces. Note that the thickness of the surface slabs, n , has been carefully tested to ensure no interaction between the two surface ends (see details in the SI).

3.2. Relative stability of surfaces

The thermodynamic stability of a given surface in general depends on the specific chemical environment. In order to identify the stable surfaces, we calculate the surface formation energy,

Figure 2: The various surface structures investigated: (a) $(0001)_M$; (b) $(0001)_B$; (c) $(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$; (d) $(10\bar{1}0)_M$; (e) $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$; (f) $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(M)}$; (g) $(11\bar{2}3)_M$; (h) $(11\bar{2}3)_B$; (i) $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$; (j) $(10\bar{1}1)_M$; (k) $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(B)}$ and (l) $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$. In the figures we also label some specific atomic planes. M atoms are in green and B atoms in grey.

σ , as a function of the B chemical potential. This is defined as

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{2A}(E_{\text{slab}} - N_M\mu_M^{\text{slab}} + N_B\mu_B^{\text{slab}}), \quad (1)$$

where, E_{slab} is the total energy of a fully relaxed slab, μ_M^{slab} (μ_B^{slab}) and N_M (N_B) are the chemical potential and the number of M (B) atoms in the surface slab, respectively, and A is the surface area.

The chemical potential of M and B (μ_M^{slab} and μ_B^{slab}) are bounded by a set of conditions. Since the surface is in equilibrium with the bulk substrate, one has the relation

$$\mu_M^{\text{slab}} + 2\mu_B^{\text{slab}} = E_{MB_2}^{\text{bulk}}. \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, since there is no precipitation of boron and metal on the MB_2 surface two additional conditions must be fulfilled, namely

$$\mu_M^{\text{slab}} - E_M^{\text{bulk}} \leq 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_B^{\text{slab}} - E_B^{\text{bulk}} \leq 0. \quad (4)$$

Finally, the heat of formation of bulk MB_2 , ΔH_f (eV/f.u.), is defined as

$$\Delta H_f = E_M^{\text{bulk}} + 2E_B^{\text{bulk}} - E_{MB_2}^{\text{bulk}}. \quad (5)$$

Here, $E_{MB_2}^{\text{bulk}}$, E_M^{bulk} and E_B^{bulk} are the total energy per formula unit of bulk MB_2 , and those per atom of the bulk hcp M metal and bulk α -rhombohedral boron, respectively. Our calculated heats of formation are 3.28 eV/TiB₂, 3.00 eV/ZrB₂ and 3.46 eV/HfB₂, respectively. These are in good agreement with previous theoretical works, reporting 3.20 eV/TiB₂,⁵ 3.02 eV/ZrB₂⁴ and 3.46 eV/HfB₂.³ Therefore, the chemical potential of B relative to bulk α -rhombohedral boron,

Figure 3: Surface formation energies of (a) B-terminated and (b) (Ti+B)- or Ti-terminated surfaces in TiB_2 . The shaded areas mark the stable regions of $(0001)_{Ti}$, $(10\bar{1}0)_{Ti}$, $(11\bar{2}3)_{Ti}$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(Ti)}$ and $(0001)_B$, when going from Ti-rich to B-rich conditions. The chemical potential of boron, $\Delta\mu_B = \mu_B^{slab} - E_B^{bulk}$, is taken with respect to that of bulk α -rhombohedral boron, $\mu_{\alpha-B}$.

$\Delta\mu_B^{slab} = \mu_B^{slab} - E_B^{bulk}$, is restricted within the range

$$-\frac{1}{2}\Delta H_f \leq \Delta\mu_B^{slab} = \mu_B^{slab} - E_B^{bulk} \leq 0. \quad (6)$$

Equation (1) for the surface formation energy can be then rewritten in terms of $\Delta\mu_B^{slab}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= \frac{1}{2A} (E_{slab} - N_M(E_{MB_2}^{bulk} - 2\mu_B^{slab}) - N_B\mu_B^{slab}), \\ &= \frac{1}{2A} [E_{slab} - N_M E_{MB_2}^{bulk} + (2N_M - N_B)(\Delta\mu_B^{slab} + E_B^{bulk})]. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The calculated surface formation energies are illustrated in Figs. 3, 4 and 5 for TiB_2 , ZrB_2 and HfB_2 , respectively. In general we find that five types of surfaces, namely $(0001)_M$, $(10\bar{1}0)_M$, $(11\bar{2}3)_M$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and $(0001)_B$, could be stabilised as the environment turns from M -rich to B-rich. This means that it is possible to design the presence of various interfaces in UHTCMCs by controlling the chemical environment during the growth of the ceramic matrix.

Beside the well-known $(0001)_{M/B}$ surfaces, the $(10\bar{1}0)_M$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and $(11\bar{2}3)_M$ are particu-

Figure 4: Surface formation energies of (a) B-terminated and (b) (Zr+B)- or Zr-terminated surfaces in ZrB_2 . The shaded areas mark the stable regions of $(0001)_{\text{Zr}}$, $(10\bar{1}0)_{\text{Zr}}$, $(11\bar{2}3)_{\text{Zr}}$ and $(10\bar{1}1)_{\text{B(Zr)}}$, when going from Zr-rich to B-rich conditions. The chemical potential of boron, $\Delta\mu_{\text{B}} = \mu_{\text{B}}^{\text{slab}} - E_{\text{B}}^{\text{bulk}}$, is taken with respect to that of bulk α -rhombohedral boron, $\mu_{\alpha\text{-B}}$.

Figure 5: Surface formation energies of (a) B-terminated and (b) (Hf+B)- or Hf-terminated surfaces in HfB_2 . The shaded areas mark the stable regions of $(0001)_{\text{Hf}}$, $(11\bar{2}3)_{\text{Hf}}$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{\text{B(Hf)}}$ and $(0001)_{\text{B}}$, when going from Hf-rich to B-rich conditions. The chemical potential of boron, $\Delta\mu_{\text{B}} = \mu_{\text{B}}^{\text{slab}} - E_{\text{B}}^{\text{bulk}}$, is taken with respect to that of bulk α -rhombohedral boron, $\mu_{\alpha\text{-B}}$.

larly notable. At the M -rich end of the surface phase diagram $(10\bar{1}0)_M$ is almost degenerate with the $(0001)_M$ surfaces, although its formation energy remains slightly higher in HfB_2 . As we move to more B-rich conditions $(11\bar{2}3)_M$ becomes stable until it gets surpassed firstly by $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and then by $(0001)_B$ at the B-rich end. Notably the pyramidal surface $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ has a wide stability range that excludes the $(0001)_B$ in ZrB_2 at B-rich end. This was also reported to be the most stable surface in Zr metal.²³

In general the B-terminated surfaces show relatively low stability, as illustrated in Figs. 3(a) through 5(a), with their surface formation energies increasing when going toward the M -rich end of the phase diagram. The $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(M)}$, $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(B)}$ and $(11\bar{2}3)_B$ surfaces have high σ and they are not stable at any value of the chemical potential. In addition the $(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$ and $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$ surfaces terminated with mixed M and B composition also have relatively higher surface formation energies. The high energy of those B-terminated surfaces is explained with the high surface strains and the largely perturbed bonding states. In contrast the $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and the $(0001)_B$ surface are thermodynamically preferred as it can be seen from the shaded areas (yellow and green) in Fig. 3(b) through Fig. 5(b). The thermodynamic preferred surfaces are associated with a relatively low cleavage energy and a low surface strain, two features that will be discussed in the following section.

3.3. Surface strain and cleavage energy

We further explore the relative surface stability by analysing the cleavage energy, E^c , the surface strain and the strain energy, U . The different values of U and E^c for various surfaces originate from the variation of the surface bonding states. Lower values of U and E^c indicate that the surface dangling bonds constitute a small perturbation in comparison of the bulk. This suggests that the surface may be stable.

The surface strain energy, U , is defined as

$$U = (E_{\text{unrelax}}^{\text{slab}} - E_{\text{relax}}^{\text{slab}})/2A, \quad (8)$$

where, $E_{\text{unrelax}}^{\text{slab}}$ and $E_{\text{relax}}^{\text{slab}}$ are the total energy of a surface slab before and after the atomic relaxation (in the unrelaxed case the surface atoms are frozen at their bulk positions). The factor 1/2 takes into account the fact that the slab has two identical surfaces.

The cleavage energy is the reversible work per unit area required to separate a bulk material along certain atomic planes to obtain isolated surfaces. It is calculated as the energy difference between the surface slabs and the bulk reference. For the cleavage modes of $[0001]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}0]_{M-B}$, $[10\bar{1}1]_{M-B}$ and $[11\bar{2}3]_{M-B}$ (cleavage between the M and B atomic planes), the cleavage energy is calculated as

$$E_{M-B}^c = (E_M^{\text{slab}} + E_B^{\text{slab}} - yE_{MB_2}^{\text{bulk}})/4A, \quad (9)$$

where, E_M^{slab} , E_B^{slab} and $E_{MB_2}^{\text{bulk}}$ are respectively the total energies of the M - and B -terminated surface slabs with reciprocal compositions (see the composition details in Section 3.1), and the total energy per formula unit of bulk MB_2 . Here, y is the total number of MB_2 formula units in the two reciprocal surface slabs to keep the mass constant. The factor 1/4 in Eq. (9) is because the two slabs have four surfaces. It is then assumed that the cleavage energy is distributed equally across all surfaces. As to the cleavage modes of $[10\bar{1}0]_{B-B}$, $[10\bar{1}1]_{B-B}$, $[11\bar{2}0]_{M+B}$ and $[11\bar{2}2]_{M+B}$, two identical surface slabs with stoichiometric compositions are separately generated. Thus, one surface slab already ensures the same composition of the bulk reference. The corresponding cleavage energy is derived as

$$E^c = (E^{\text{slab}} - yE_{MB_2}^{\text{bulk}})/2A. \quad (10)$$

Here, E^{slab} is the total energy of the surface slab.

The way in which the cleavage develops, determines both the orientation and the termination of the surfaces. These largely influence the surface stability. The calculated cleavage energies of MB_2 ($M=\text{Ti/Zr/Hf}$) are reported in Table 2. Among the three MB_2 ceramics ZrB_2 presents the largest lattice constants (thereby a looser atomic stacking) and has the lowest E^c values. They systematically increase when going from $[10\bar{1}1]_{B-B}$, to $[11\bar{2}2]_{M+B}$, to $[11\bar{2}3]_{M-B}$, to $[11\bar{2}0]_{M+B}$, to

$[0001]_{M-B}$, to $[10\bar{1}0]_{M-B}$, to $[10\bar{1}0]_{B-B}$ and lastly to $[10\bar{1}1]_{M-B}$ for all the three compounds. The low cleavage energy of $[10\bar{1}1]_{B-B}$ and $[11\bar{2}3]_{M-B}$ explains the energetic preference for the $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ and $(11\bar{2}3)_M$ surfaces. Note that the cleavage energy is only equal to the surface energy when the cleaved terminations are identical, but the converse is not necessarily true. The latter are also affected by the chemical environments and the surface strains. Although the $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$ surface has relatively low cleavage energy, it also displays high surface strains, as illustrated in Fig. 6, which lessen its thermodynamic stability. Furthermore, the trend across the cleavage energy is not directly correlated to the interlayer bonding strength, since the latter is influenced by the change of bonding densities on the various surfaces as well.

Table 2: The surface cleavage energies (E^c , J/m²) in MB_2 materials.

Cleavage modes	TiB ₂	ZrB ₂	HfB ₂
$[10\bar{1}1]_{B-B}$	3.87	3.55	4.67
$[11\bar{2}2]_{M+B}$	4.07	3.70	4.85
$[11\bar{2}3]_{M-B}$	4.68	4.16	5.35
$[11\bar{2}0]_{M+B}$	4.80	4.17	5.36
$[0001]_{M-B}$	4.85	4.51	5.74
$[10\bar{1}0]_{M-B}$	5.29	4.59	5.86
$[10\bar{1}0]_{B-B}$	5.44	4.73	5.94
$[10\bar{1}1]_{M-B}$	6.42	5.55	6.85

The calculated surface strains, ΔL_{ij} , are plotted in Fig. 6. These are measured as the relative change in interlayer distances L_{MiMj} and L_{BiBj} , respectively for the M - and B -terminated surfaces (the index i/j label the atomic planes as defined in Fig. 2). The general trend is similar for TiB₂, ZrB₂ and HfB₂ with the strain mainly localized in the first three surface layers. The outermost surface layers of $(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$, $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$ and $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$ exhibit expansion strains, while the others show contraction strains due to the inward relaxations. The surface strains are reduced quickly as we move away from the surface. When comparing different orientations we notice that extremely high strains are displayed by the B -terminated surfaces. A fact that indicates the large geometry disturbance near those surfaces. The large strains in the $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$ surface lead to the severe distortion of the six-member boron rings, as displayed in the inset of Fig. S1 in the SI.

Figure 6: The surface strains (U , %) in (a) TiB_2 , (b) ZrB_2 and (c) HfB_2 , measured by the change of interlayer spacing with respect to the bulk.

However, no surface reconstruction is observed in all cases, which is consistent with previous investigations.^{3,4,5} This could be related with the metallic characters of those materials as proven by the projected density of states of Fig. 7.

Another way to analyze the overall strain state consists in looking at the surface strain energies, U , tabulated in Table. 3. Starting from ZrB_2 , U is much smaller for the Zr-terminated surfaces than for the B-terminated ones. In particular the $(10\bar{1}0)_{\text{Zr}}$, $(0001)_{\text{Zr}}$ and $(11\bar{2}3)_{\text{Zr}}$ surfaces show rather similar low strain energies, which reflects their relative stability as discussed before. In contrast, B-terminated surfaces store more strain energies than the M -terminated ones. This is associated to their large surface strains as shown in Fig. 6. Such result points to a high energy state of the B-terminated surfaces. These, in fact, need to adapt the dangling bonds at the surface,

which largely deviates from the originally cut ones. Thus, in general, B-terminated surfaces with high surface strains appear less stable than their M -terminated counterparts. TiB_2 and HfB_2 behave similarly to ZrB_2 , as summarized in Table 3. Again this correlates nicely with the results of Figs. 6, which show that the termination species is the main factor determining the surface strain. The thermodynamic preferred surfaces are the synergistic outcomes of atomic planes with low cleavage energy and low strain energy.

Table 3: The surface strain energies (U , J/m²) in MB_2 materials.

Surfaces	TiB_2	ZrB_2	HfB_2
$(0001)_M$	0.03	0.04	0.01
$(10\bar{1}0)_M$	0.10	0.02	0.02
$(11\bar{2}3)_M$	0.08	0.06	0.04
$(10\bar{1}1)_M$	0.07	0.08	0.03
$(0001)_B$	0.10	0.10	0.07
$(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$	0.04	0.19	0.12
$(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$	0.19	0.25	0.21
$(11\bar{2}3)_B$	0.44	0.62	0.52
$(10\bar{1}0)_{B(M)}$	0.14	0.37	0.25
$(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$	0.75	0.95	0.82
$(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$	0.22	0.20	0.19
$(10\bar{1}1)_{B(B)}$	0.26	0.55	0.42

In order to explore the origin of the relative surface stability, the projected density of states (PDOS) of bulk ZrB_2 and that of the outmost surface layers in differently oriented surface slabs are calculated and presented in Figs. 7(a-l). The bonding in bulk ZrB_2 is dominated by the in-plane covalent σ bonds among the B atoms (sp^2 hybridization from s , p_x and p_y orbitals), and the interlayer Zr-B bonding (Zr: d -B: p_z and Zr: d -B: sp^2). The PDOS minimum at around the Fermi level, E_F , of bulk ZrB_2 [illustrated by the light grey curves in Figs. 7(a)-7(l)] results from the covalent Zr-B bonding. This splits the Zr d states leaving a pseudo-gap around E_F . Such PDOS reduction disappears for all the surface atoms [shown by the black curves in Figs. 7(a)-7(l)]. In the case of the Zr-terminated ones, Figs. 7(a), 7(d) and 7(g), the PDOS around E_F originates mainly from the Zr d electrons and resembles that of metallic Zr. This is different from the situation of

(0001)_B in Fig. 7(b) and (11 $\bar{2}$ 0)_{M+B} in Fig. 7(c), where the PDOS peaks attributed to the B p_z and sp^2 orbitals emerge at E_F as a result of the partial loss of Zr-B coordination at the surfaces. In these cases the B sp^2 bonds are marginally disturbed by the formation of the surfaces. For the B-terminated surfaces in Figs. 7(e), (f), (h) and (k), we notice the high energy states corresponding to the unfilled B sp^2 orbitals slightly above E_F . It indicates that the surface formation has strongly affected the in-plane covalent B-B bonds. Such change of the B sp^2 PDOS suggests a weakening of the surface bonds resulting in an overall less stable surface. Finally, the surface PDOSs of (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(M)} and (11 $\bar{2}$ 2)_{B(M)} from low E_c cleavage modes only show slight disturbance in Fig. 7(i) and (l).

3.4. Conclusions

In conclusion we have studied the surface stability of TiB₂, ZrB₂ and HfB₂, three promising compounds for the fabrication of ultra-high temperature ceramic matrix composites. Five types of surfaces, namely (0001)_M, (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_M, (11 $\bar{2}$ 3)_M, (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(M)} and (0001)_B are found to be stable, when progressively moving from M -rich to B-rich conditions. Notably, this is the first time that the (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_M, (11 $\bar{2}$ 3)_M and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(M)} surfaces are analysed and their stability predicted, in agreement with a number of experimental observations. In general we have found that the M -terminated surfaces settle with low surface strains. At the same time the (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(M)} surfaces benefit from a low cleavage energy. The thermodynamically preferred surfaces are the synergistic results of the easy cleavage orientation and the relatively low surface strains, owing to less disturbed surface bonding states. Our work provides a comprehensive analysis of the surface formation of TiB₂, ZrB₂ and HfB₂, an information that is crucial to explore their use in UHTCMCs.

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Figure 7: Planar averaged projected density of states (PDOS) for the surfaces atoms (black curves) of (a) $(0001)_M$; (b) $(0001)_B$; (c) $(11\bar{2}0)_{M+B}$; (d) $(10\bar{1}0)_M$; (e) $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(B)}$; (f) $(10\bar{1}0)_{B(M)}$; (g) $(11\bar{2}3)_M$; (h) $(11\bar{2}3)_B$; (i) $(11\bar{2}2)_{M+B}$; (j) $(10\bar{1}1)_M$; (k) $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(B)}$ and (l) $(10\bar{1}1)_{B(M)}$. The PDOS is compared with that of bulk ZrB_2 (light grey curves).

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4. Figure captions

Fig.1: The V - T curve of ZrB₂ calculated by using PBE, PBE+D2 and PBE+D3 methods. The theoretical results are compared with the experimental data of Ref.²¹ Note the excellent agreement provided by the PBE+D2 scheme.

Fig. 2: The various surface structures investigated: (a) (0001)_M; (b) (0001)_B; (c) (11 $\bar{2}$ 0)_{M+B}; (d) (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_M; (e) (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_{B(B)}; (f) (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_{B(M)}; (g) (11 $\bar{2}$ 3)_M; (h) (11 $\bar{2}$ 3)_B; (i) (11 $\bar{2}$ 2)_{M+B}; (j) (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_M; (k) (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(B)} and (l) (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(M)}. In the figures we also label some specific atomic planes. M atoms are in green and B atoms in grey.

Fig.3: Surface formation energies of (a) B-terminated and (b) (Ti+B)- or Ti-terminated surfaces in TiB₂. The shaded areas mark the stable regions of (0001)_{Ti}, (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_{Ti}, (11 $\bar{2}$ 3)_{Ti}, (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(Ti)} and (0001)_B from Ti-rich to B-rich condition. The chemical potential of boron, $\Delta\mu_B = \mu_B^{\text{slab}} - E_B^{\text{bulk}}$, is taken with respect to that of bulk α -rhombohedral boron, $\mu_{\alpha-B}$.

Fig.4: Surface formation energies of (a) B-terminated and (b) (Zr+B)- or Zr-terminated surfaces in ZrB₂. The shaded areas mark the stable regions of (0001)_{Zr}, (10 $\bar{1}$ 0)_{Zr}, (11 $\bar{2}$ 3)_{Zr} and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1)_{B(Zr)}

from Zr-rich to B-rich condition. The chemical potential of boron, $\Delta\mu_{\text{B}}=\mu_{\text{B}}^{\text{slab}}-E_{\text{B}}^{\text{bulk}}$, is taken with respect to that of bulk α -rhombohedral boron, $\mu_{\alpha\text{-B}}$.

Fig.5: Surface formation energies of (a) B-terminated and (b) (Hf+B)- or Hf-terminated surfaces in HfB_2 . The shaded areas mark the stable regions of $(0001)_{\text{Hf}}$, $(11\bar{2}3)_{\text{Hf}}$, $(10\bar{1}1)_{\text{B(Hf)}}$ and $(0001)_{\text{B}}$. The chemical potential of boron, $\Delta\mu_{\text{B}}=\mu_{\text{B}}^{\text{slab}}-E_{\text{B}}^{\text{bulk}}$, is taken with respect to that of bulk α -rhombohedral boron, $\mu_{\alpha\text{-B}}$.

Fig. 6: The surface strains (U , %) in (a) TiB_2 , (b) ZrB_2 and (c) HfB_2 , measured by the change of interlayer spacing with respect to the bulk.

Fig. 7: Planar averaged projected density of states (PDOS) for the surfaces atoms (black curves) of (a) $(0001)_{\text{M}}$; (b) $(0001)_{\text{B}}$; (c) $(11\bar{2}0)_{\text{M+B}}$; (d) $(10\bar{1}0)_{\text{M}}$; (e) $(10\bar{1}0)_{\text{B(B)}}$; (f) $(10\bar{1}0)_{\text{B(M)}}$; (g) $(11\bar{2}3)_{\text{M}}$; (h) $(11\bar{2}3)_{\text{B}}$; (i) $(11\bar{2}2)_{\text{M+B}}$; (j) $(10\bar{1}1)_{\text{M}}$; (k) $(10\bar{1}1)_{\text{B(B)}}$ and (l) $(10\bar{1}1)_{\text{B(M)}}$. The PDOS is compared with that of bulk ZrB_2 (light grey curves).